

MOMENTS OF THE SMARANDACHE FUNCTION

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Given a positive integer n , let $P(n)$ denote the largest prime factor of n and $S(n)$ denote the smallest integer m such that n divides $m!$

This paper extends earlier work [1] on the average value of the Smarandache function $S(n)$ and is based on a recent asymptotic result [2]:

$$\left| \{n \leq N : P(n) < S(n)\} \right| = o\left(\frac{N}{\ln(N)^j}\right) \quad \text{for any positive integer } j$$

due to Ford. We first prove:

Theorem 1.
$$E(S(N)^k) = \frac{1}{N} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^N S(n)^k = \frac{\zeta(k+1)}{k+1} \cdot \frac{N^k}{\ln(k)} + O\left(\frac{N^k}{\ln(N)^2}\right)$$

where $\zeta(x)$ is the Riemann zeta function. In particular,

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln(N)}{N} \cdot E(S(N)) = \frac{\pi^2}{12} = 0.82246703\dots$$

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln(N)}{N^2} \cdot \text{Var}(S(N)) = \frac{\zeta(3)}{3} = 0.40068563\dots$$

Sketch of Proof. On one hand,

$$L(k) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln(n)}{n^k} \cdot E(P(n)^k) \leq \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln(n)}{n^k} \cdot E(S(n)^k) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln(N)}{N^{k+1}} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^N S(n)^k$$

The above summation, on the other hand, breaks into two parts:

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln(N)}{N^{k+1}} \cdot \left(\sum_{P(n)=S(n)} P(n)^k + \sum_{P(n)<S(n)} S(n)^k \right)$$

The second part vanishes:

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln(N)}{N} \cdot \left(\sum_{P(n) < S(n)} \left(\frac{S(n)}{N} \right)^k \right) \leq \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln(N)}{N} \cdot \left(\sum_{P(n) < S(n)} 1 \right) = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln(N)}{N} \cdot o\left(\frac{N}{\ln(N)} \right) = 0$$

while the first part is bounded from above:

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln(N)}{N^{k+1}} \cdot \left(\sum_{P(n)=S(n)} P(n)^k \right) \leq \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln(N)}{N^{k+1}} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^N P(n)^k = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\ln(n)}{n^k} \cdot E(P(n)^k) = L(k)$$

A formula for $L(k)$ was found by Knuth and Trabb Pardo [3] and the remaining second-order details follow similarly.

Observe that the ratio $\sqrt{\text{Var}(S(N))} / E(S(N)) \rightarrow \infty$ as $N \rightarrow \infty$, which indicates that the traditional sample moments are unsuitable for estimating the probability distribution of $S(N)$. An alternative estimate involves the relative number of digits in the output of S per digit in the input. A proof of the following is similar to [1]; the integral formulas were discovered by Shepp and Lloyd [4].

Theorem 2.

$$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} E \left(\left\{ \frac{\ln(S(N))}{\ln(N)} \right\}^k \right) = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{x^{k-1}}{k!} \cdot \exp \left(-x - \int_x^{\infty} \frac{e^{-y}}{y} dy \right) dx = \begin{cases} 0.62432998 & \text{if } k = 1 \\ 0.42669576 & \text{if } k = 2 \\ 0.31363067 & \text{if } k = 3 \\ 0.24387660 & \text{if } k = 4 \\ 0.19792289 & \text{if } k = 5 \end{cases}$$

The mean output of S hence has asymptotically 62.43% of the number of digits of the input, with a standard deviation of 19.21%. A web-based essay on the Golomb-Dickman constant 0.62432998... appears in [5] and has further extensions and references.

References

1. S. R. Finch, The average value of the Smarandache function, *Smarandache Notions Journal* 9 (1998) 95-96.
2. K. Ford, The normal behavior of Smarandache function, *Smarandache Notions Journal* 9 (1998) 81-86.
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4. L. A. Shepp and S. P. Lloyd, Ordered cycle lengths in a random permutation, *Trans. Amer. Math. Soc.* 121 (1966) 350-557.
5. S. R. Finch, *Favorite Mathematical Constants*, website URL <http://www.mathsoft.com/asolve/constant/constant.html>, MathSoft Inc.